

Effect of Parental and Teacher in Child's Behavior (Study on Psychological Conditions after Entering into Open Society (Post Covid)

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Abstract:- Child development is a series of processes which involves various factors. The major factor affecting the child's development is his/her home environment. Child's parents influence more and more. In this case study, the series of events of the child is recorded and how his attitude, characters, behavior, and his cognitive ability is developed. This case study also tries to interpret the influence of school, lock down, online class and modern technology. To understand his developmental phases, various theories of the psychologists were considered. Motivation was given to the child to change his behavior. An alternative method of teaching was adopted to improve the child's learning.

Keywords:- Child development, home environment, behavior, teaching.

I. INTRODUCTION

The study is about the relational effect of the child's behavior before and after the Covid lock-down. In this Study, a child of age 9 was taken. Their parents approached the author for taking home tuition. Their demand is to complete the Child's Daily homework. As a tutor, the author needs to analyze the mental, emotional, personal interest, friends, likes and dislikes of the children. The study is fully about the effect of children who attend Online classes and physical classes. **UNICEF (2013)** states that "The early years of life are crucial not only for individual health and physical development, but also for cognitive and social-emotional development. This statement laid the foundation for this study.

A. Point to be considered

- **Age:** 9
- **Grade:** 4th

B. Home members:

- Grandmother (Primary caretaker), Sister (13 age), Mother and Father (vocationally available)
- When the instructor started his 1st class, he is so quiet and unanswerable
 - After 1 to 2 weeks, it is observed that he struggles to write
 - He is left-handed
 - His parent (Mother) **told that, he is so good, before they leave him with his Grandparents**
 - He is taken care by his Grandparents
 - It is observed that he was disturbed by his parent's absence
 - His way of speaking with elders is not good

- He has only one elder sister

C. Initial stage

Up to 2nd standard, he does normal schooling. He automatically gets ready and goes to the tuition after school. During the covid period, his entire 3rd standard and 1st half of the 4th standard is only online.

His parents recognize his behavior is altered. He became so dependent on smartphones and online media.

After 1 month of tuition, he is still quiet and unanswerable. Then the instructor decided to interpret his personal knowledge, interest, school life, friends but not about his teachers.

It is found that he is interested in science and math by asking him, "whether you want to know, how the fan rotates or how to write a song or story?". He said that he needs to know about the fan's rotation and how the plant is growing. Then later it is found that he is actively involved in science and mathematics subjects, while he is not interested in his mother language and second language.

During the teaching of the instructor in the child's home, he often changes his position and walks away from the instructor without permission. It irritates the instructor and often the instructor warns him not to do such actions. But he doesn't change this behavior.

D. Over kindnesses

As a lovable parent, his mother shows him love and affection. According to **Garrison**, over affection affects the child and that results in the lack of self-confidence. After 5 weeks, his mother returned home. Whenever the instructor starts to take tuition, he tells his mother that he doesn't need tuition. His mother convinced him by saying that if he successfully completed the homework, she would offer a toy to him and then he would feel happy and sit calmly. Later, somewhere in the middle of the tuition, he got off and went to his mother without permission whenever written work was assigned by the instructor. Whenever his mother showed her anger toward his disobedience and mistakes, he remained silent. Only after her apologies, he tried to calm down.

According to the 4th stage (**Industry Vs Inferiority**) of Erick Erickson Psycho-Social Development theory, the child feels encouraged when the mother convinces his child by reinforcement i.e. if he attends the tuition then a toy will be given to him. This encourages the child, and he feels good, so he continues to attend the tuition. Whenever he

shows disobedience (while assigning written work), his mother shows her anger, so **Inferiority** is developed in the child and calms down.

This way of activity influences the Child's behavior. A child can easily develop this attitude and waits for other actions to act normal and unable to think of his mistakes or actions.

E. Uncompleted and un-checking

In the initial days of teaching in tuition, the work is assigned to learn math's tables and his mother language (Tamil) letters. This assignment needs to be done every day when the instructor leaves him and tells him that he will ask a question from tables and letters. This assignment is still incomplete because the problem is on both sides. Whenever the instructor asked about his assignment, he simply laughed and said, 'I am unfinished'. The instructor asked his grandmother about his activity after tuition hours. She said that he didn't take his notebooks after the instructor left and told that he cries when she makes a strict order.

His crying triggers his mother and she can't bear it. So, his grandmother leaves him in his own way. In the early days, the instructor gave assignments, but he didn't check them. He also didn't talk about the assignment. Later, he forgot about the assignment. After 2 weeks, he suddenly asked about the assignment. And the student said that he didn't do the assignment and became silent.

F. Motivation

During the middle of the instructions, the instructor motivated him by relating the child's comic heroes in real life. He wanted to be a good boy. He asked for gifts from his mother if he remains a good boy and improves his performance in upcoming exams. After these sessions, he performs good actions for 2 days. After 2 days he was back to his original state. Hence, he can't be able to remain in the same excited state for more than two days.

Motivation speech by elders greatly influences the children. So, the instructor told him about the real-life achievements, and he asked, "Are you a good boy or bad boy?" he replied "I am a good boy"

Set of rules and punishments were given to the child. He also accepted those rules and punishments. In front of him the rules and punishment were written on the paper and signed then pasted on a wall.

The rules are,

- Accept the failure
- Respect the elders
- Don't waste the time
- Don't lie
- Be healthy

The Punishment are given based on breaking the above rules

- For 1st time - using mobile phone is restricted for 1 day
- For 2nd time - using mobile phone is restricted for 2 days
- For 3rd time - using mobile phone is restricted for 1 week

On the 2nd day after the paper was pasted, it was unavailable. On enquiry, his mother said that during last night's fight, it was torn.

Hence **rules and punishment are initially accepted and excited. Over a period, it was not being followed.**

Suggestion actions: when he tears the rule paper, his mother should react and take the proper action on him. This incident will create an effect on child.

G. Effect of different teachers

Different people's teaching affects the child's attitude. This is the most important effect that was experienced from that student. After 2 months, on questioning about his teachers and the way of handling when the homework is unfinished, he answered that his language (Tamil) and Science teacher will punish him if he didn't complete the homework.

He particularly talks about the punishment that was given by his language teacher; she beats up with a scale vertically. After this statement the instructor asked him, "If your teachers gave a punishment, you would do their homework correctly but, I am not giving punishment, so you are not obeying my order?" He smiles and stays silent.

Hence, it is inferred that the **way of handling affects the child's behavior.**

Also, in the way of teaching methods, students are greatly influenced by the schoolteachers. In mathematics, the instructor solved the problems in different methods and styles of writing in notebooks than his schoolteachers. The child doesn't accept the way, because he believes that the method and style followed by his schoolteachers is correct. So, he refused the new methods.

This shows that the independent thinking of students is affected by **schoolteachers.**

According to Jean Piaget's theory of cognitive development, this child falls under the category of the concrete operational stage (7 to 11 years). In this stage, the child has acquired logical thinking based on what he perceives or sees. They could solve the problem given by the teacher with his logical thinking but if the same math problem is taught in a different way, the child won't accept because of the lack of complex or independent thinking.

During the revision test, while the instructor was revising the portion, there was a spelling mistake on a word that he wrote. Instruction was given to him to rectify the mistake. But he is not ready to accept it. He said that this word was written by his schoolteacher, so he feels that it is correct. The instructor suggested the child to ask his mother. His mother said that there is a spelling mistake. So, the school teaching is effective and prevailing.

H. Development in unlinked systems

In the way of learning, students follow the series system. It greatly influenced the students' learning. Whenever they revise the book back questions or the already well-known concepts, they follow the series of questions i.e., the questions are arranged based on the sequential concept.

In tuition, the instructor teaches him about the Basics of time and clock with examples. He learned about the relationship and the equalities of second with minutes and minutes with hour. In the textbook, the question is based on the following series: Convert minutes to seconds, Seconds to minutes, hours to minutes.

In the class, a test was conducted based on the book's series of questions. His answering timing is low, and he easily answered. Then the questions are altered with different values. Now the time to complete the answer is a little higher than before.

Then the pattern of question was completely altered. The instructor asked him to convert a day to seconds. He was a little confused and started thinking. Then the instructor linked the question with the previous link. He immediately made a calculation and answered.

Hence the level of thinking develops when the **series of links breaks and relinks with the known concepts**. And here the new knowledge is constructed when his early knowledge is induced.

I. Change in actions

Initially he was guided with patience and sweet words and the instructor spoke to him gently when he made mistakes and work undone. After 50 days of teaching, the instructor changed his way of speaking and actions.

The instructor showed his anger when the child disobeyed his orders and disrespected the elders.

On the 1st day of his change in behavior: The instructor remained silent and walked away from the child after teaching hour. Also, the instructor informed about this behavior (Note: on that day, his father is available at home).

On next 2 days, the child changes his attitude towards the instructor. He properly answered and obeyed.

So, the presence of parents while studying improves the child's behavior and attention.

J. Disciplinary actions

In one session, he behaves unusually. The instructor was preparing the child for the Revision test.

The first exam is a language (Tamil) paper. While preparing, he didn't show an interest in writing the test. His mother forced him to read and write the letters. He refused and threw the pencil box away. The instructor showed his anger against this particular action. The child's mother told the instructor to take the action accordingly, then she left. Once again, the instructor questioned the boy "Is this the way that a good boy behaves?" He replied, "I am not a

good boy". Then the instructor asked, "Are you willing to study or write the test?" He opted for studying.

But the child lay down his head and remained silent. The instructor took the scale and beat on the table and raised his voice to wake up and study. He obeys the instructor's order, and he sat straight.

II. HENCE SUDDEN CHANGE IN TEACHER GREATLY AFFECTS THE CHILD'S BEHAVIOR AND ACTIONS

A. Self-realization

Analyzing children's behavior is a time-consuming process. Analyzing by self is more complex. It is very difficult for children. The instructor made an evaluation of the child by making the child himself evaluate his behaviors, capabilities, skills, interests. He tells about his behavior, that he is making a mistake and trying to rectify phase by phase. This self-realization occurs when **motivation and comparison(with the childhood days of the instructor and his mother) is made**.

B. Self-Acceptance

In one session the instructor told him about Truth and Courage. The child asked, "If I am getting punished for not making a mistake, what will I do?". The instructor answered that you should stand against the punishment.

Then he replied, "If I stand against my punishment, mam will beat me once again".

This statement shows the acceptance of punishment by students from teachers without proper investigation. This effect will cause a change in behavior and way of speaking. Defending against the truth is **demotivated** by this kind of actions taken by teachers.

C. Inference

By made a series of observations the main factors affecting the student's characters are

- School teachers
- Online classes
- Parental actions
- Tuition teacher

As stated above, those three factors greatly influenced and brought about changes in student's development. The 2nd factor is not taken seriously, because it is temporary. But this factor also changed the way the student behaves. Apart from parents, schoolteachers greatly took part in a child's development. They learn what they see, they do what teachers do to them, they speak how teachers teach, they act how teachers act. As stated above in self-acceptance, teachers will play a major role in character building.

III. CONCLUSION

School is a miniature society where the child interacts with others and learns more things. This child falls under the category of gang stage period, where the child's playmates influence social development. Because of social interaction many good social behaviors like sympathy, group cooperation, and ideas about good and bad social behavior will gradually develop. All these social interactions majorly occur in school. But because of the lock down there is lack of social interaction and this affects the child's social development.

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